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Towards trajectory-based latent space control for human-robot collaboration

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Abstract

In manual assembly, human-robot collaboration (HRC) research activities aim to improve the manual handling of parts. For this purpose, latent space control has been investigated by several research groups. However, control problems have shown limited applicability for various frame-based latent space models. The objective of this work is to determine if positional control is principally possible for trajectory-based latent spaces. Therefore, we investigate how ‘reach’ trajectories that are constrained in the target position map to a latent space that has been derived from functional principal component analysis (fPCA). A multivariate normality test is conducted to analyze the target-constrained position in the latent space, followed by mapping between the latent and Cartesian spaces. Results show that for linear shifts in the target ‘reach’ position, Gaussian modes in the latent space move along a vector in the latent space. Additionally, Gaussian mixtures occur at the target point where different motion styles are chosen for reaching. Results suggest that positional control may prove feasible for the considered type of latent space.

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1. Introduction

In manual assembly, human-robot collaboration (HRC) research activities aim to improve the manual handling of parts by coupling human and robot motions that highly anticipate the human motion behavior with high mutual care. This includes the study of human motion models and their naturalness. Several human motion models, e.g., statistical [15], deep-learning [9], and bio-mechanical [20] have been presented for HRC motion modelling. These motion models intend to synthesise random motions to understand human motion behavior and capabilities of the workplace, e.g., for planning and handling operations. However, controlling variant rich and natural human motion for two workers sharing tasks and spaces has remained challenging. In a human-robot collaboration context, two workers, i.e., a human and a robot, who handle an object together, are expected to share a collaboration state that engages individuals to be able to achieve the desired goal during handling tasks [17]. Such a collaboration state involves a shared trajectory, defined roles and responsibilities, open communication and interaction methods. Thus, each worker will be able to complete the task while also relying on the other’s contributions, creating a dynamic of trust and interdependence between human and robot.

Understanding how humans perform handling tasks jointly and how transferring this knowledge to human-robot co-workers standing at opposite ends of the workplace (see Figure 1) involves how humans visually observe to match their grips, coordinate to lift simultaneously and move it while continuously monitoring obstacles or direction changes. Similarly, how both co-workers non-verbally intercommunicate the timing and speed at which they will place the object may unlock the next level of human-robot collaboration methods. Transferring the collaboration style of the two humans into human-robot collaboration based on human motion behavior analysis helps to design collaborative robots workplace design (c. [19]). However, the success of the human-robot collaboration, in the context mentioned above, depends on the human motion generation model and analysis, which includes replacing the motion behavior of, e.g., Participant II (see Fig. 1) by the collaborative robot model. In this case, a new control design requirement that lets the collaborative robot handle the object jointly with Participant I and be responsive to Participant I’s actions and environmental conditions in real time.

Control design, e.g., Latent Space (LS) control, which several research groups have investigated (c. [10]), has shown limited applicability for various frame-based LS models. Previous works, e.g., [14] that use probabilistic models for digital human motion modeling observed hand motion going beyond the

Fig. 1: Proof of concept for transforming the way humans collaborate to human-robot for object handling scenario using simulation tools (e.g., Unity 3D environment).

target point for picking with the right hand. According to the result analysis given in [14], though most of the path repetitions to reach the same target are close to the maximum density of the motion frame distributions, some of them show variations around the majority. Motion generation of such variant rich may risk motion harmonics that are rejected due to low explainable variances. Specifically, LS may lose fine-grained details when precise control is desired. While frame-based LS are widely recognized in reducing the dimensionality of high dimensional data, they may suffer when handling real-time control tasks which may not align with the requirements such as responsiveness and adaptability (c.[3, 1]). For this reason, the current work aims to investigate if positional control is principally possible for trajectory-based LS.

2. Objective

The current work aims to investigate whether target-constrained trajectories based on latent space controllers for human-robot collaboration are principally possible for positional control. Target position-constrained ‘reach’ trajectories mapping Cartesian Space (CS) to a Latent Space (LS) are employed. Here, the reach motion is clustered based on spatial densities, and the distribution property is analyzed. According to assumptions given in [14], distributions that are normal likely yield natural human motion, and based on this assumption, the normality of the distribution, e.g., whether it yields Gaussians or Gaussian Mixtures in the latent space must be determined, and their shift will be analyzed based on target position.

3. Related works

Human motion generation models are often modeled by tracking the motion of human body skeleton joints over time. This includes prediction of future trajectories that are conditioned on previously captured trajectories. This can be a deterministic approach that estimates points over future trajectories or a probabilistic approach that learns a distribution over future trajectories using latent variables [21].

Further works investigated a control design using latent space (LS) to control human trajectories. Early research in the application of LS control has focused mainly on frame-based approaches, where a single static input (frame) is mapped to a corresponding latent representation. For example, in [6], vari-

ational autoencoder (VAE), model represents a full-body and partial-body human motion separately for controlling specific body parts. It uses past sequences to predict future human motions. Similarly, the works of [5] introduced Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) that comprise a generative model that captures distribution of the data and discriminative model for estimating the probability of the outcome based on the training data.

Applying LS for human-robot control in several works yielded mixed results, especially in frame-based settings. The works of [12] showed frame-based LS yielding sufficient performance for policy learning in simpler environments; however, for dynamic and complex tasks like human-robot collaboration that require real-time decision-making and fine-grained control, the performance was degraded.

To solve the limitations in frame-based models, a trajectory-based LS model was proposed in [16] that employs a recurrent neural network (RNN) architecture. This LS was trained to learn the current state and the robot’s future trajectory. The approach was proved effective in tasks requiring fine motor control and anticipation of human actions, such as cooperative object manipulation and assembly tasks. In the same manner, [13] applied LS to predict human actions over short intervals by modeling human motion and robot responses. According to their result, the proposed LS model could enable a robot to adjust during real-time tasks like shared object handling and collaborative assembly. In this context, LS models represent sequences of movements that capture the underlying temporal dynamics essential for predicting and adapting to human behavior.

Furthermore, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks have been particularly effective at modeling time dependent latent space mapping for early detection and prediction of human actions (cf. [18]). In, [11] a three-layer LSTM network is used for recognizing human actions based on three dimensional skeleton joints data, which enable robots make decision whether to interrupt the current task or not. These LSs are encoded to capture motion patterns over time. In works presented in [2], proposed controllable motion generation via Latent Consistency Model (LCM) which applies text-conditioned human motion generation based on latent diffusion models. Networks such as LSTM, and diffusion models are known for their predictive power but often lack interpretability, making it hard to explain what is happening inside the layers (c.[4]).

In order to extend the application of LS control and overcome its inherent limitations, particularly in frame-based con-

trol, space partitioning approach which has been proposed by [15] and extended further by [8]. The lack of direct interpretability or physical meaning makes the applicability of LS-based controls more challenging, mainly to translate into actionable control commands, such as joint angles, torques, or force feedback (c. [14]).

4. Method

The current study proposes a novel method that examines the possibility of implementing positional control named TLSC, as illustrated in Fig. 2, by mapping the desired target positions of the reaching hand position to Latent Space (LS) to identify a suitable area in LS for a given hand constraint. The main contribution is the human motion naturalness evaluator block that is extended based on previous works of Min et al. [15], and Manns et al. [14] for studying human motion variability experienced in manual assembly. The human motion naturalness evaluator block comprise the mapping of the latent and Cartesian space and analysis of the distribution mode in LS from which robot models generate TCP paths. Motion trajectories generated by motion model for ‘reach’ an object is employed. This ‘reach’ motion model is a probabilistic human motion model namely Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM), which is set up to maximize expectations by fitting Gaussian models to samples in high-dimensional spaces. Such high-dimensional spaces are considered latent spaces, which are derived from functional principal component analysis (fPCA). A fPCA is conducted so that each motion is represented by low-dimensional vector [3].

The final hand-reaching position from the human movement is mapped to the LS to analyse the predicted human trajectories. The spatial mapping is validated by comparing predicted and actual target hand positions based on trajectory accuracy. Furthermore, the human motion naturalness evaluator examines whether the mapping produces Gaussians or Gaussian Mixtures in the LS and evaluates if Gaussian modes shift linearly along a vector with changes in the target ‘reach’ position. This approach also reveals how Gaussian Mixtures drive the selection of varied motion styles to perform natural reaching tasks.

4.1. Latent and Cartesian space mapping

The current study uses the probabilistic model to generate a dataset of random samples of human motion for reaching tasks in a Cartesian Space (CS). The desired target positions of the reaching hand, which depend on the entire human movement, were used as spatially constrained. The hand position is chosen as a measuring point to regenerate the whole human motion. Each sample of human motion is described by multiple principal components (PCs) in the LS. The first few PCs capture the main variations in human motion.

Human motion is spatially constrained to follow a reaching task, and it is normally distributed with a specific mean and variance. To investigate the relationship between points (mean and covariance) in the LS for a given desired target point of the reaching hand, first, a spatial partitioning is carried out for the

desired target positions in a CS. Each region in a partitioned space can be seen as a constraint. The distribution of points in the LS is then analysed to determine whether the region defined by constrained movements follows a normal distribution. If so, this region could generate infinite movements that satisfy the hand constraint. Python Dictionary is used to store the data in a key-value pair format to map the reaching points in the CS to the complete motion data in the LS; the model is interpretable and explainable. Another possible method to identify the relationship would be the Gaussian process, which is challenging to scale and becomes very computationally intensive with a large amount of training data [14]. Alternatively, the Multivariate Polynomial Regression (MPR) method could be used to integrate the desired reach point with the mean value of the human motion for a reaching task. However, using the mean alone gives a single of the most probable solutions for the observed human motion. Using multivariate normal distribution to detect an area in the latent space may be another effective way for a real-time application. They provide a basis for determining the influence of the distribution in the latent space on the prediction. Finally, the influence of the distribution in the latent space on the precision of a mapping will be examined.

4.2. Shifts in mode on Latent Space (LS) vector

This subsection discusses whether the mapping yields Gaussians or Gaussian mixtures in the LS and whether Gaussian modes shift linearly along a vector as the target ‘reach’ position changes. First, the LS of a constrained motion is examined to see whether it is approximately described by a multivariate normal distribution using the Henze - Zirkler test [7]. The HZ test rejects multivariate normality if the absolute value of the statistic test is greater than the appropriate critical value. The distribution is analyzed to observe its shift in LS based on the constraints set in CS. This helps assess how the constraints influence position and orientation within LS.

4.3. Positional control concept

This subsection discusses how the proposed method predicts the selection of varied motion styles to perform reaching tasks for a given constraint. The accuracy of the predicted trajectories is analysed. For this purpose, the closest normal distributions of the given target position in the partitioning space are calculated and then used to predict human movements in the LS. The predicted hand trajectories are generated using the human motion model. The resulting trajectories were evaluated in terms of whether they fulfilled the respective constraint by comparing the predicted final hand position with the actual given target points in CS.

5. Simulation and Results

The probabilistic human motion model is constructed using fPCA and GMM, as described in the Method section. This model is used to generate 10 million random samples of the

Fig. 2: A high-level illustration of a TLSC method toward trajectory based positional control. The human trajectory is used as an input based on LS model comprising nine spatial principal component vectors $\{P_{c1}, P_{c2}, \dots, P_{c9}\}$, which is mapped to the CS. The dashed box represents the new contributions while the complete system highlights future developments.

‘reach’ movement task; the “randomness” follows the probability distribution of the GMM. Then, the human movements were described by multiple PCs in the LS, and the motion is spatially constrained to follow a reaching task. The LS contained the main PCs for all data points, and the number of PCs in the fPCA automatically selected to retain 95% of the information in the data [14]. In this model, 15 main components were identified, where the first nine represent the spatial control of the movement. The other six represent the temporal, which is beyond the scope of this work. For each random sample, the target position of the right-hand movements is determined in CS. Finally, the coordinates of the reaching hand and their corresponding points in LS were recorded.

Figure 3 presents the reaching hand positions in a CS and the values of the main components (PC1 to PC9) for five cases (a, b, c, d, e). Column 1 visualizes the final hand positions in CS. Columns 2 to 9 show how PC1 correlates with PC2 through PC9. The spatial constraints chosen in each case can be seen in orange in each figure. The reaching hand movements are constrained around specific points in CS, with each case having a distinct space centre: (20, -55, 115), (78, -50, 150), (30, -60, 50), (30, -20, 40), and (25, -60, 70) cm for cases (a) to (e). In each case, these centres define the spatial boundaries for the reaching hand’s position.

The motion dataset is filtered for data points whose distance from a specific point in CS must not exceed 5 cm. These points were highlighted in orange and displayed across the entire dataset in CS and LS to make their relative position visible (see Figure 3) and to see how points in the LS of spatially constrained movements are distributed.

5.1. Spatial partitioning

A spatial partitioning is carried out for the reaching hand positions in a CS. The whole space has been divided into small cubes with a side length of 3 cm. After defining partitions, all generated datasets were assigned to the cubes, and 14,916 cubes were identified. However, only cubes with at least 1,000 data points were considered, and the number of cubes is reduced to 2,912. This results in a data loss of 21.37% of the original data points. Figure 4(right) shows the layout of the cubes in CS. This leads to the two clusters being separated from each other (see Figure 3).

5.2. Multivariate normal distribution tests

To illustrate how the corresponding points in the LS of spatially restricted movements are distributed, the Henze-Zirkler test is carried out for each spatial division for the desired target positions in CS. The test made clear whether these are distributed approximately normally.

The Henze-Zirkler test is implemented to determine the HZ values at which the null hypothesis is not rejected, and the results are shown in Figure 4(middle). The results reveal that the average HZ values of each cube in the upper and lower clusters are 1.39 and 1.13, respectively. The HZ values are mostly constant in both clusters. However, both clusters show outliers in one area. The results show that the critical value of the HZ value at nine dimensions and a significance level of $\alpha = 5\%$ is around 0.99.

5.3. Mapping

This section discusses how the endpoint of the reaching hand in CS relates to all motion data in LS using a Python dictionary. It stores data with a unique identifier for each subdivision to map from a set of keys (cube centres in CS) to an associated set of values (mean and covariance of each PC in LS). Using the multivariate normal distribution to identify areas within LS facilitates real-time application by quickly assessing the predictive trajectories. Since the speed of calculations plays a crucial role in the HRC application, a performance test is carried out to compare the time required for determining 1000 human motion predictions using the Python dictionary and MPR. The Python dictionary approach is significantly faster, requiring only 0.17 seconds to complete the task. This only involved finding the mean and covariance in the LS, not calculating the resulting human motion. In comparison, the seventh-degree MPR model takes 2.97 seconds. This highlights the Python dictionary’s efficiency, making it a better option for real-time applications in human-robot collaboration (HRC) where speed is essential.

Finding a spatial mapping of the reaching hand to the mean and covariance of each PC in the LS enables the generation of different motion styles for reaching various target points. The accuracy of trajectory generation for different styles of reaching motions is evaluated, as explained in the following section.

Fig. 3: Target hand positions and principal component relationships with constrained movements in Cartesian Space (CS)

Fig. 4: Layout of the cubes, the blue points represent the centre of the cubes. .

5.4. Parameter prediction according to a multivariate normal distribution

The mapping results give a distribution of the points in the LS of a spatially restricted movement in the two clusters. To evaluate the accuracy of trajectory prediction for any given target points in CS, the closest centre point of the cube needs to be selected for a random given point. Then, the corresponding normal distribution is determined from the points in the LS. One hundred random motions were constructed from the respective normal distributions, which produce ‘reach’ movements. The final positions of the reaching hand were recorded.

In order to determine the accuracy of trajectory prediction, the distance between the final positions of the reaching hand and the given test point is determined; the distance can be seen as an error. The obtained final positions of the reaching hand will not precisely reach the center of the cube. The average error

is calculated and shown in Figure 4(left). The results show that the errors for the upper and lower clusters are 1.95cm and 1.57cm, respectively. Furthermore, the final positions of the reaching hand were examined to see what percentage of these were in the respective cube. Among the reaching hand points derived from random points of a multivariate normal distribution, 51.40% and 66.75% fell within the corresponding cubes in the upper and lower clusters, respectively.

6. Discussion

The results shown in Figure 3 clarified how ‘reach’ trajectories are constrained in the target position map to human motion, which is described by nine PCs in the LS. This analysis also reveals the nature of these distributions, showing that they tend to be normal (Gaussian) distributions with a specific mean and variance.

The human motion is spatially constrained to follow a reaching task, and it is normally distributed with a specific mean and variance for each PC. This can be seen even more clearly in the lower cluster (see Figure 3a and b) than in the upper cluster (see Figure 3c and d). The results conclude that a small spatial restriction in CS leads to a larger scatter in the LS. The scatter density decreases with the distance from the center. However, the constrained movement shown in Figure 3e generates two clusters, as the constrained movement in the CS occurs between two reaching motion tasks; this indicates that the nature of these distributions tends to be Gaussian Mixtures. The desired target positions of the reaching hand position identify a relevant region in the LS for a given constraint.

The results from the spatial mapping of the given target positions of the reaching hand position to the points (mean and covariance) of each PC in the LS enable us to understand the position controller characteristics. For example, systematically examining how changes in X, Y, and Z coordinates affect the mode of LS and orientation of the distribution, the shift from scenario (a) to (e) shows significant changes in the mode position and orientation (see Figure 3) for PC1 vs PC3, PC1 vs PC5 and PC1 and PC6. When the human motion goes from high to low-density area, PC3, PC5, and PC6, with respect to PC1 weights are more responsive for an LS-based position controller.

The proposed method is validated by comparing predicted and actual target hand positions based on trajectory accuracy. The computational time and the accuracy of trajectory prediction for different styles of reaching motions are acceptable for low tolerance (~ 2 cm) positioning in the context of HRC and manual assembly, which focuses on the potential for improving robotic assistance in collaborative tasks.

7. Conclusions and Future Work

Trajectory-based Latent Space Controllers (TLSC) method highlights the significance of target position constrained control on spatial trajectory bundles which is critical for improving real-time capability of human robot collaboration. Based on human motion naturalness, future works should focus on the investigation of role based human robot interaction with high anticipation and high mutual care.

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